

Research on the Value Implication of Sports Boosting the Great Revival of the Chinese Nation

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Abstract: The 20th National Congress of the CPC is a very important conference held at a critical moment when the Chinese people of all ethnic groups embark on a new journey of building a socialist modern country in an all-round way and march towards the second century goal. Deeply understand the twenty themes of the CPC, the call of the times of "three musts", the major political achievements of "two establishment", and the important connotation of "five firmly grasp". To study, publicize and implement the spirit of the 20th National Congress of the CPC is the primary political task and top priority of China's sports system at all levels at present and in the future. The report of the 20th National Congress of the CPC clearly put forward the task of accelerating the construction of a sports power, adhere to the people as the center, and build a sports power with the people enjoying the fruits of sports development as the purpose. Accelerating the construction of a sports power, bearing the hope of national prosperity and national rejuvenation, is the internal call to realize the Chinese Dream of the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation.

Keywords: Xi Jinping; the Communist Party of China; The spirit of the Twentieth National Congress; Sports power; Value implication.

1. INTRODUCTION

October 2022 is the occasion of the 20th CPC National Congress after the 100th anniversary of the founding of the CPC. Over the past century, the CPC has united and led the people of all ethnic groups throughout the country through the great historical process of "standing up - getting rich - getting strong". All the way, it has made remarkable achievements, and China is also moving towards the goal of becoming a world sports power, and is getting closer and closer to the realization of the Chinese dream of the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation. On the occasion of the victory of the 20th National Congress of the CPC, we should deeply learn and understand and deepen the implementation of the spirit of the General Secretary's important statement on sports work. We should take the important statement as the guide, "scientifically study and judge the new situation facing sports development, adhere to the problem orientation, focus on key areas and key links, deepen reform and innovation, and constantly create a new situation for sports development". At the same time, the COVID-19 is still spreading around the world, which has brought severe tests and great challenges to human life, health and safety and world peace and development. Although the domestic situation has stabilized and the epidemic prevention and control has entered a new stage of "normalization", the adverse effects of the epidemic on the development of national sports still exist. At this special historical moment of the centennial of the founding of the Communist Party of China, the layout of the plan, and the elimination of diseases and plagues, the research on the important discussion of sports related work in the spirit of the Twentieth National Congress and its value implications can not only promote the in-depth and systematic construction and development of the important spirit, but also properly respond to the impact of the COVID-19, scientifically guide the development process of Chinese sports Accelerate the building of a sports power and a healthy China to provide ideological guidance and practical guidance.

2. COMPLETE STATEMENT ON SPORTS IN THE REPORT OF THE 20TH NATIONAL CONGRESS OF THE CPC

On October 25, 2022, Xinhua authorized to release the party's 20 report the united struggle for the all-round construction of a socialist modernization country, in the "eight, promote cultural self-confidence, self-improvement cast the socialist culture new glory" part mentioned sports, about sports as: "extensive the national fitness activities, strengthen youth sports work, promote the comprehensive development of mass sports and competitive sports, speed up the construction of sports power."

Held on October 16, the opening meeting of the twentieth National Congress of the Communist Party of China, xi jinping, general secretary on behalf of the 19th session of the central committee to the conference entitled "holding the great banner of socialism with Chinese characteristics for the all-round construction of modern socialist country and united struggle" report, put forward "promote the comprehensive development of mass sports and competitive sports, speed up the construction of sports power".

On October 16, Xinhua News Agency was authorized to release an excerpt of the Party's 20th report, "Xi Jinping proposed to promote cultural confidence and self-improvement, cast a new glory of socialist culture", describing sports as "strengthen youth sports work, promote the all-round development of mass sports and competitive sports, and accelerate the building of a strong sports country".

On October 22, the 20th National Congress of the CPC adopted the Resolution of the 20th National Congress of the CPC on the Report of the 19th Central Committee, and approved the report of the 20th National Congress of the CPC.

3. THE SPIRIT OF THE 20TH NATIONAL CONGRESS OF THE CPC INVOLVES THE INTERPRETATION RELATED TO SPORTS

3.1 Understand the spirit of the 20th National Congress of the CPC as the direction of sports development

Since the founding of the People's Republic of China, China has never participated in the Olympic Games in the past to the current Olympic Games gold (award) card list, which fully shows that the Communist Party of China attaches great importance to the cause of sports. After restoring its legal seat in the Olympic Games, China participated in the Winter Olympic Games for the first time in 1980 and the Summer Olympic Games for the first time in 1984. In the decades of development, China practiced the Olympic country honor glory plan, and achieved satisfactory results, which greatly inspired the national spirit. The state will put sports in the "Five in one" and "Four comprehensive" strategic layout planning, and strive to solve the bottleneck problem of sports. We will focus on improving the health level of the whole nation, adhere to the coordinated development of competitive sports and mass sports, establish an integrated development mechanism, and at the same time, improve the development mechanism of youth sports, fully tap social resources, and vigorously promote sports reform.

The Party's 20th Congress has once again identified General Secretary Xi Jinping as the core of the CPC Central Committee and the core of the whole Party. It is the call of The Times, the historical choice and the aspiration of the people that enable the whole Party and the backbone of the whole people to lead the great ship of "Fuxing", establish the guiding position of Xi Jinping Thought on Socialism with Chinese Characteristics for a New Era, provide the ideological banner, theoretical arm and sharp weapon, and provide a scientific action guide for promoting the great cause of national rejuvenation. To understand the decisive significance of "Two established", more consciously maintain the core of xi jinping, General Secretary of the CPC Central Committee, the core position of the party, more consciously maintain the authority of the party central committee with comrade Xi Jinping as the core and centralized and unified leadership, fully implement xi new era the ideas of socialism with Chinese characteristics, unswervingly in ideological political action with the party central committee with comrade xi for the core keep highly consistent. Deeply understand the party's 2 major themes, deeply understand the "Three must" call of The Times, deeply understand the "Two established" major political achievements, deeply understand the "Five firmly grasp" important connotation. The Communist Party of China is the core of the leadership for the cause of building socialism with Chinese characteristics. To promote the development of sports, we must adhere to the unified deployment of the Party. General Secretary Xi Jinping stressed, "We should uphold the Party's leadership over all work, improve the Party's ability to set the direction, plan the overall situation, formulate policies, and promote reform, and ensure that the Party commands the overall situation and coordinates all parties."

Deeply understand the mission of the new journey of sports work in the new era. Sports systems at all levels should have a deep understanding of this arduous task and sacred mission, and give full play to the comprehensive value and diversified

functions of sports in building the health of the people, gathering energy for great rejuvenation, enabling social development, casting soul for confidence and strengthening global sports in the process of building a modern socialist country in an all-round way.

3.2 Firm the party's twenty great spirit for the leadership of sports development

Accurately grasp the profound connotation of sports power. First of all, the spirit is strong, to provide the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation. Sports should be used to shape the national constitution and spirit, and to stimulate the patriotic enthusiasm of the Chinese people. Secondly, the system is strong, adhere to the socialist sports development road with Chinese characteristics. We must adhere to the Party's overall leadership over sports work, serve the central tasks of the Party and the state, and adhere to the development model of competitive sports dominated by the nationwide system. The third is the material strength, realize the modernization of sports development guarantee conditions. We should constantly improve the mechanism of sports investment, modernize sports facilities and equipment, and promote the prosperity and development of sports consumption. Fourth, it is comprehensively strong, forming a good situation of all-round development of all aspects of sports. We should strengthen competitive sports, mass sports, sports industry, sports culture, and sports science and technology, and achieve all-round development among regions, projects, and people. Fifth, the integration is strong, so that sports are fully integrated into the overall development of the country. To promote higher integration of sports and economic and social development, deeper integration of sports and related industries, and stronger integration of sports and global sports development.

Studying, publicizing and implementing the Party's 20th spirit well is the primary political task and top priority for the national system at all levels at present and for a period to come. Departments each unit should be in accordance with the "five firmly grasp" requirements, exactly study the party's 20 report and the newly revised party constitution, seriously grasp the party's 20 put forward new ideas, new ideas of new deployment requirements, to the party's spirit of twenty have a good grasp of, learn deep enlightenment deeply, to guide the work practice.

The party's twenty great spirit as the leadership, strive to create a new situation of building a strong sports country. We need to unify our thinking, build consensus, and integrate our thoughts and actions into the decisions and arrangements of the CPC Central Committee and General Secretary Xi Jinping's important remarks on sports. General Secretary Xi Jinping's important discourse on sports is rich in connotation, profound in thought and clear in requirements. It is an important part of Xi Jinping Thought on Socialism with Chinese Characteristics for a New Era and provides fundamental guidance for promoting the reform and development of sports in the new era. We should take the implementation of General Secretary Xi Jinping's important remarks on sports as the fundamental magic weapon for planning our work and solving problems, strengthen our consciousness of thinking and action in implementation, and ensure that the decisions and arrangements of the CPC Central Committee and The State Council on sports work take root and achieve practical results.

3.3 Adhere to the people-centered thought of sports development

The foundation and blood of the Communist Party of China lies in the people. In his 20th CPC report, General Secretary Xi Jinping made it clear that we must firmly grasp the major principle of "upholding the philosophy of people-centered development" on the way forward. Adhering to the philosophy of people-centered development embodies the Party's ideals, beliefs, nature, purpose, and original mission. It is also a profound summary of the Party's struggle and practical experience. Developing sports around the center and promoting people's all-round development is also the starting point and goal of sports work. Sports are inseparable from the people, and sports are more inseparable from the people. Athletes winning gold and silver in the international arena is the sacred mission of the Party and the people to give the Chinese sports delegation to win glory in the international arena. To enhance the ability of sports to win glory for the country, we need to rely on a solid mass foundation. Only by expanding the mass foundation of sports, can we form a hierarchical selection mechanism and build a transmission belt for the training of top sports talents. China's excellent achievements in sports in the international arena can greatly encourage the people's enthusiasm for sports and attract more people to participate in the cause of sports, thus expanding the mass base. Therefore, the development of sports can not be separated from the people, and the development results of sports can stimulate the people's enthusiasm to participate in the cause of sports. We will strengthen Party building in the new era in sports, serve the people, and more importantly, we must uphold the unswervingly and comprehensively govern the Party with strict discipline. We will give top priority to political development, strengthen political responsibility for governing and governing the Party, continue to improve Party conduct, uphold integrity and fight corruption, and improve the conduct of our officials.

The fundamental purpose of building a strong sports country and developing sports is to seek for the welfare of the people. Any decision of the Party is based on the position of the people, proceeding from the interests of the people, and relying on the strength of the people, and benefits all the people from the fruits of building a strong sports country and the development of sports.

3.4 Comprehensively deepen and promote the coordinated development of sports

The coordinated development of sports can be divided into balanced and coordinated development and overall and coordinated development.

3.4.1 Balanced and coordinated development of sports undertakings

There is unbalanced development of sports in China. General Secretary Xi Jinping has affirmed the great progress in China's sports industry for many times, but we still need to strengthen the weak links. In particular, in the "three big balls", there is a significant gap between China and the world's strong players. There is not only unbalanced development in the overall project, but also unbalanced development in individual projects. In season, there is an imbalance between the development of summer and winter projects, and between the eastern and western regions. This requires under the leadership of the Party, reasonable layout, overall planning, scientific allocation of resources, promote the cause of sports to achieve a leap from quantitative change to qualitative change, the comprehensive implementation of coordinated and sustainable development strategy.

3.4.2 Overall planning and coordinated development of sports undertakings

From the perspective of the overall and coordinated development of sports undertakings, sports undertakings should lead the coordinated development of mass sports and sports industry. Sports strength is the dominant indicator of national sports strength, and mass sports is the basis for realizing the long-term development of a strong sports country. The good development of mass sports can expand the number of people participating in sports and broaden the channels of talent selection for sports undertakings. The national team winning glory for the country in international competitions can stimulate people's enthusiasm for sports and drive the development of mass sports. The high participation in mass sports will surely drive the development of the sports industry. The development of sports industry is an important symbol to realize the cause of sports power, and the current contribution of sports industry to the national economy is low, and the future development potential is large. To this end, China has made strategic arrangements for the sports industry. By 2035, the sports industry will become the pillar industry of the national economy. The sports industry is closely related to competitive sports and mass sports. Competitive sports provide the sports industry with high-level competition resources, develop sports events and cultivate market subjects. The development of the sports industry provides market space for the development of competitive sports, which helps to improve the level of sports products and services. To promote the coordinated development of mass sports, competitive sports and sports industry, we should take into account overall consideration, give full play to their respective characteristics and contribute to the building of a strong sports country.

Based on the two development factors, we will comprehensively deepen and promote the coordinated development of sports undertakings. We should fully implement the national strategy of national fitness, further improve the comprehensive strength of competitive sports, adhere to and improve the national system, follow the development path of competitive sports with Chinese characteristics, actively explore the development path of the "three big balls" with Chinese characteristics, and do a good job in the preparation for the Paris Olympic Games and the Milan Winter Olympics. We will strengthen youth sports work and promote the high-quality development of the sports industry. We will vigorously promote the Chinese sports spirit and promote foreign sports exchanges and cooperation. We will strengthen the construction of sports practices, vigorously promote sports reform, and prevent and defuse major risks and challenges in the field of sports.

4. THE IMPLICATION OF THE TWENTIETH SPIRIT OF THE PARTY ON THE VALUE OF SPORTS UNDERTAKINGS

4.1 Enriched and strengthened Xi Jinping Thought on Socialism with Chinese Characteristics for a New Era

With the constant change of the situation at home and abroad, how to go on the socialist road has become a major issue of The Times. Around this issue, the Communist Party of China is committed to emancipating the mind, seeking truth from facts, keeping pace with The Times, seeking truth and being pragmatic, and forming Xi Jinping Thought on Socialism with

Chinese Characteristics for a New Era. In the grand system of Xi Jinping Thought on Socialism with Chinese Characteristics for a New Era, the relevant discourse on sports is an important part. Xi Jinping Thought on Socialism with Chinese Characteristics for a New Era makes it clear that socialism with Chinese characteristics is, under the leadership of the Communist Party of China, to realize socialist modernization and the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation, adhere to the thought of people-centered development, and achieve common prosperity for all the people. In the new era, sports must thoroughly implement Xi Jinping Thought on Socialism with Chinese Characteristics for a New Era. The achievements of sports in China cannot be separated from the leadership of the Communist Party of China. Under the leadership of the Party, the planning of sports in the overall situation of the cause of socialism with Chinese characteristics is also the fundamental guarantee for promoting the development of sports. Maintaining the people-centered approach is the pursuit of the Communist Party of China. To develop sports, we must develop people-centered sports. The glory of sports for the country is to inspire the national spirit, stimulate the enthusiasm of the masses to participate in sports, promote the development of sports industry, and finally benefit the achievements of the construction of a sports power to the people. Realizing the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation is the greatest dream of the Chinese people in modern times. General Secretary Xi Jinping has pointed out the dialectical relationship between the dream of becoming a strong sports country and the Chinese dream, and the dream of becoming a strong sports country is an important part of realizing the dream of the Chinese dream. Therefore, the dream of becoming a strong sports country should be integrated into the grand system of the Chinese dream.

4.2 The ideological banner and program of action leading China's sports work in the new era

With the successful convening of the fortieth Congress of the Party, General Secretary Xi Jinping stands in the overall strategy of national rejuvenation, attaches importance to sports work, and puts forward new ideas and new ideas, providing ideological banner and action program for sports work in the new era. It is under the guidance of General Secretary Xi Jinping's important discourse on sports work that the Party's leadership over sports work has been comprehensively strengthened. Strengthen the "four consciousness", firm "four self-confidence", do "two maintenance", adhere to the party's leadership over the cause of sports is the strong backing for the development of sports in the new era.

Under the guidance of General Secretary Xi Jinping's important remarks on sports work, the deployment for accelerating the construction of a sports power is increasingly clear. As General Secretary Xi Jinping has pointed out, "Building a sports power is an important part of the Chinese people's realization of the two centenary Goals." To strengthen the construction of a strong sports country, it is necessary to enhance the sports strength, and fully implement the coordinated and sustainable sports development strategy.

Give full play to the role of competitive sports in stimulating the people's enthusiasm to participate in sports, promote the development of sports industry and stimulate market vitality. Building a strong sports country is all-round. We should not only build a strong country in competitive sports, but also build a strong country in mass sports and sports industry. Promoting the coordinated development of competitive sports, mass sports and the sports industry is an important measure to meet the people's yearning for a better life.

4.3 Inherit and innovate the comprehensive development of Marxist sports thought

Marx mentioned many times the social function of sports, which is an important way to promote social development. It plays an indispensable role in improving personal quality and promoting the all-round development of people. The Marxist sports view is an important part of the Marxist educational theory system, and also an important theoretical basis of the socialist sports thought. General Secretary Xi Jinping has been talking on sports, especially in the party's 20th report, fully inherited the Marxist sports thought.

The sociality of Marxist sports thought is reflected in that sports increases the opportunities of social communication. Through the development of sports, we will inspire the national spirit and promote the healthy development of the masses. Sports competitions can dilute the conflicts between nations, overcome the obstacles of the social system, and build a platform for the communication between people. Under the condition of socialist market economy and in the market economy environment of increasingly putting interests first, the spirit of fairness, justice and win-win cooperation advocated by sports plays a leading role in purifying social atmosphere, purifying market relations and leading social culture.

The theory of individual comprehensive development of Marxist sports thought is reflected in sports to excavate the human potential, and the sports spirit of "faster, higher and stronger" makes human beings constantly challenge their limits. In

developing sports, the results ultimately belong to the people. Through the development of sports, enable more people to participate in sports, so as to promote more people to participate in sports, enhance physical fitness, adjust the psychological state, maintain the balance and stability of individual body, and realize the all-round development of individuals. In the 20th report of the Party, the people emphasizes the people as the logical starting point and the development of human beings as the value purpose. In the field of sports, the innovation is realized on the basis of Marxist sports thought.

4.4 Make unique original theoretical contributions in the history of world sports development

General Secretary Xi Jinping's important discussion on sports, especially in the party's 20th annual report, complies with the trend of The Times, is forward-looking, and is China's original theoretical contribution to world sports. General Secretary Xi Jinping's discussion on sports contains the beautiful vision of "world harmony", showing China's responsibility as a major country contributing to the global sports development. In the face of global terrorism and unilateralism, sports, as an important carrier of international exchanges, can promote the integration of different cultures and ethnic groups, enhance mutual understanding, and play an important role in seeking common ground while shelving differences. Display the advanced culture of all countries on the Olympic sports stage, the world will help them learn from each other and achieve win-win cooperation, and promote the building of a community with a shared future for mankind.

General Secretary Xi Jinping has deeply summarized the law of the development of sports, scientifically answered a series of questions such as sports being suitable for the communication and integration of different ethnic groups in the world, and established the consensus that sports belongs to the people of the world.

5. CONCLUSION

The party's 20th report clearly puts forward the tasks and requirements of accelerating the building of a strong sports country, uphold the Party's overall leadership over the cause of sports, vigorously promote the deepening of reform, and comprehensively optimize the coordinated development of competitive sports, mass sports and the sports industry. Give full play to the institutional advantages of the nationwide system and integrate the resources of all parties. We will continue to put the people first and build a strong sports country with the aim of the people enjoying the fruits of sports development. Accelerating the construction of a strong sports country carries the hope of national prosperity and national rejuvenation, and is the inner call for realizing the Chinese dream of the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation.

REFERENCES

- [1] The General Administration of Sport of China. Further study Xi Jinping's important discourse on sports [M]. Beijing: People's Publishing House, 2022:341.
- [2] Yang Guoqing. Xi Jinping's important discussion on the success of the Beijing 2022 Winter Olympics [J]. Journal of Chengdu Institute of Physical Education, 2022,48 (1): 1-7.
- [3] Zhao Na, Shi Yan. Five problems, practical ideas and development goals of the study of sports legal construction in China [J]. Journal of Shenyang Physical Education Institute, 2022,41 (2): 86-93.
- [4] Ding Yongliang, Yang Guoqing. The rich connotation and main origin of General Secretary Xi Jinping's important discourse on sports work [J]. Journal of Beijing Sport University, 2018,41 (10): 8-18.
- [5] Xu Zixuan, Zhang Yuchao. Research on Xi Jinping's Important discourse on sports work in the New Era [J]. Journal of Nanjing Institute of Physical Education, 2021,20 (11): 9-15.
- [6] Zhang Xiuliang. Analysis of the origin of General Secretary Xi Jinping's important discourse on sports work [J]. Journal of Nanjing Institute of Physical Education, 2021,20 (7): 27-31.
- [7] Ma Di Yuan. Research on Xi Jinping's important discussion on sports Power [D]. Harbin: Northeast Forestry University, 2021:14-16.
- [8] Wang Meng, Qu Yanchao. The historical evolution, theoretical connotation and important value of the century-old sports thought of the Communist Party of China [J]. Physical Education and Science, 2021,42 (4): 1-7.
- [9] Sun Guoyou, Sang Feiming. The logical starting point, practical pursuit and value purpose of Xi Jinping's important discourse on sports work [J]. Physical Education Research, 2019,2 (6): 40-46.